

THE EFFECTS OF PARTICLES SIZE AND VOLUME FRACTION ON MICROSTRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF IN-SITU NANO TiB₂/Al7050 COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In-situ nanoparticles reinforced metal matrix composites (In-situ Nano-PRMMCs) demonstrate better mechanical properties due to smaller particles size, less wedge angle of particles and more uniform distribution. The main aim of this research is to study the effects of TiB₂ particles size and volume fraction on mechanical properties such as tensile and compressive Young's modulus, crack growth and fracture toughness of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites. Experiments along with the numerical simulations by using the XFEM (Extended Finite Element Method) technique and Analytical formulation were conducted to elaborate the effects of geometry and volume fraction of nanoparticles on the mechanical properties.

A new relation based on the microstructure model shown by the Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) is developed to predict the equivalent modulus of elasticity. The geometry and volume fraction are the main independent variables which affect the overall output of the formula. Relative error between experimental results and equivalent tensile Young's modulus predicted by the formula is less than 5%.

According to the experimental results, tensile Young's modulus, compressive Young's modulus and shear Young's modulus of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites increase greatly with increase of particles volume fraction. But there is no significant improvement in tensile strengths, compressive strengths and shear strengths.

The numerical results based on the XFEM technique show that nanoparticles can prevent the propagation of micro-cracks effectively. But the fracture toughness of in-situ nano TiB₂/Al7050 composites with volume fraction 3.0%, 5.6% and 7.8% content of particles decreases by 6.41%, 7.75%, 12.43%, respectively, compared with matrix Al7050. It shows that fracture toughness of the composites decreases with the increase of particles size and increases with more uniform particles distribution. By considering uniformity, shape, size and volume fraction of particles, in-situ PRMMCs can be designed and produced with better mechanical properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

In-situ nanoparticles reinforced metal matrix composites (Nano-PRMMCs) exhibit better mechanical properties because of smaller particles size, less wedge angle of particles and more uniform distribution^[1]. Nano-PRMMCs, the abbreviation of nanoparticles reinforced metal matrix composites, combine the advantages of ceramic particles and matrix alloy, which has the higher strength as compared to homogeneous material^[2, 3]. Due to the low density, high specific stiffness, high specific strength and low coefficient of thermal expansion, Nano-PRMMCs have wide applications in the areas of aviation, automotive, aerospace, electronics and other industries^[3]. As an important branch of PRMMCs, in-situ Nano-PRMMCs have better mechanical properties due to the smaller particles size, less wedge angle of particles and uniform distribution of particles^[4]. In addition, the bond strength between matrix and particles is higher than the PRMMCs manufactured in traditional technology. The macro-mechanical properties of PRMMCs are greatly dependant on particles size, so as the particles size of the composites decreases the mechanical properties will improve significantly. The size of TiB₂ of the composites in this paper ranges from 50nm to 200nm and volume fraction of TiB₂ is 3.0%, 5.6% and 7.8% respectively.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Mechanical Properties Experiments

The tensile, compressive, and torsional experiments are performed to study the effects of particles size and volume fraction on the mechanical properties of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites. The experimental results for mechanical properties of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites with different particles size and volume fraction are shown in Table 1 to 3. The experimental results show that the mechanical properties of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites are greatly affected by the reinforcing particles. The failure models are typical and the failure positions are mostly in the middle of specimens.

For compressive experiments, the compressive strength of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites with volume fraction 3.0%, 5.6% and 7.8% content of particles increases by 1.58%, 2.56%, 6.46% respectively and the compressive modulus increases by 3.38%, 4.03%, 6.91% respectively, compared with matrix Al7050.

For tensile experiments, the tensile modulus of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites increases with the increase of TiB₂ particles volume fraction, especially the tensile modulus of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites with volume fraction 7.8% content of TiB₂ particles is improved by 16.3% compared with matrix Al7050, but the Poisson's ratio and elongation decrease with the increase of TiB₂ particles volume fraction. The tensile strength and yield strength of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites are almost same as matrix Al7050.

For torsional experiments, the shear modulus of the in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites with volume fraction 3.0%, 5.6% and 7.8% content of particles increases by 5.16%, 7.11% and 11.94% respectively, compared with matrix Al7050. The torsional strength increases with the increase of TiB₂ particles volume fraction, but the improvement is not great.

Particles volume fraction	Compressive strength/MPa	Compressive modulus/GPa
0%	836.91	63.95
3.0%	865.18	64.96
5.6%	870.64	65.59
7.8%	894.78	68.08

Table 1: The compressive properties of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites.

Particles volume fraction	Tensile strength/MPa	Tensile modulus/GPa	Poisson's ratio	Yield strength/MPa	elongation
0%	639.93	69.55	0.337	586.49	5.65%
3.0%	631.52	71.04	0.319	591.90	2.23%
5.6%	636.22	75.63	0.316	595.98	1.73%
7.8%	633.38	80.77	0.315	599.75	0.95%

Table 2: The tensile properties of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites.

particles volume fraction	torsional strength/MPa	shear modulus/GPa
0%	343.80	29.24
3.0%	360.08	30.75
5.6%	345.48	31.32
7.8%	352.12	32.73

Table 3: The torsional properties of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites.

The experimental results show that the compressive strength, tensile modulus and shear modulus improve greatly when TiB₂ particles are blended. This improvement of the stiffness of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites is great, while the strength of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites isn't improved greatly compared with the matrix Al7050. On the contrary, the elongation and Poisson's ratio are reduced slightly.

2.2 Microstructure Observation by SEM

In-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites have better macroscopic mechanical properties than matrix Al7050 due to its microstructure [5]. The microstructures of the in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites with volume fraction 3.0%, 5.6% and 7.8% content of particles are shown in Fig 1 to 3 respectively, which are observed in SEM images under different magnification levels. In the meantime, the damage forms and fracture mechanisms are studied based on the fracture micromorphology of tensile specimens observed in SEM images, shown in Fig 4 to 7.

Fig 1: Microstructure of specimens with different particles volume fraction (a: 3%, b: 5.6%, c: 7.8%) by SEM with 2000-time magnification.

Fig 2: Microstructure of specimens with different particles volume fraction (a: 3%, b: 5.6%, c: 7.8%) by SEM with 10000-time magnification.

Fig 3: Microstructure of specimens with different particles volume fraction (a: 3%, b: 5.6%, c: 7.8%) by SEM with 50000-time magnification.

Fig 4: Centre through crack of particles by SEM with 10000-time magnification.

(a) The $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al7050}$ interfacial debonding; (b) The TiB_2 particles breakage.
 Fig 5: The main damage patterns by SEM with 2000-time magnification.

(a) Secondary crack; (b) Microcrack propagation along the $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al7050}$ interface.

Fig 7: The fracture micromorphology of tensile specimens by SEM with 70-time magnification.

The observations from SEM images of in-situ $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al7050}$ composites are as follows:

- The particles show the zonal distribution and are non-uniformly distributed in the matrix, shown in Fig 1;
- The particles aggregation can be observed in the SEM images and the average size of aggregates is $1\mu\text{m} \sim 2\mu\text{m}$, shown in Fig 2;
- The particles' size is uniform and ranges from 50nm to 200nm. Moreover the sharpness of particles is irregular but has no obvious sharp edges. The particles agglomeration is more obvious with the increase of particles volume fraction, shown in Fig 3;
- Compared with the traditional technique, the in-situ method reduces the particles' size to nanosize (the average size is 150nm) and reduces the internal defect of particles, which makes the PRMMCs have better macroscopic mechanical properties due to the better interfacial bonding and more uniform particles distribution, shown in Fig 1 to 3;
- Combining the Fig 4 to 7, the fracture mechanism can be concluded that TiB_2 particles breakage and the $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al7050}$ interfacial debonding^[6] are the main damage patterns of in-situ $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al7050}$ composites, and the fracture process can be divided into three stages: damage initiation, micro-crack propagation and final failure^[7]. The stress concentration often appears in the interface between particles and matrix, which causes the particles breakage and interfacial debonding^[8, 9]. When in-situ $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al7050}$ composites are pressed, the centre through crack of

particles, microcrack and interfacial debonding grow more preferentially in the TiB₂/Al7050 interface. The crack propagation process is shown in Fig7.

3 THEORETICAL ANALYSIS AND NUMERICAL SIMULATION

3.1 A New Formula for Predicting Young's Modulus of Nano-PRMMCs

Particles size, volume fraction, the uniformity of particles distribution and the properties of matrix alloy are main factors of Young's modulus of Nano-PRMMCs [6]. During the past few decades, previous studies on in-situ PRMMCs by experiments, theoretical analysis or numerical simulation were carried out and the cell models [9, 10] were proposed to deduce the formulae for predicting Young's modulus of Nano-PRMMCs, but the resulting analytical predictions of the traditional formulae were not in good agreement with experimental results [9]. A new model has been proposed in this paper based on the improvement of previous models, and the simplified assumptions of this model are as follows:

- The particles are uniformly distributed in the matrix and exist in large quantities [12];
- The substrate does not undergo plastic deformation and is cylindrical;
- Particles are cylinders;
- Equal stress and equal strain distribution are found in the particles [13];
- In the process of tensile loading, the interface between matrix and particle remains intact.

According to the assumptions, Representative Volume Element [14] (RVE) is selected as the analysis object when we study the effects of TiB₂ particles size and volume fraction on Young's modulus of Nano-PRMMCs on the mesoscopic scale.

A new model called "Unit cell of one particle" has been built as the Fig 8

Fig 8: The simplified calculation model of equivalent young's modulus of Nano-PRMMCs

In Fig 8, a , b , and ε represent the diameter, height and strain of the unit cell respectively. Superscript 'p' and 'm' denote the strain of particle and matrix respectively. Then the equivalent young's modulus of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites can be expressed as follows:

$$E_C = \frac{E_M \left[(E_P - E_M)(\pi a^2 b - 4b) + 4E_P \right]}{4 \cdot [E_P(1-b) + E_M b]} \quad (1)$$

In the Equation (1), E_C , E_M , and E_P are the equivalent young's modulus of this unit cell, the young's modulus of the matrix, and the young's modulus of particle respectively. In the meanwhile a and b are the geometry factors, which can be obtained by SEM images and similarly can be used to determine the volume fraction. By defining the particle aspect ratios S which equals b/a , the predicted values of equivalent young's modulus of Nano-PRMMCs with different particles size and volume

fraction are listed in Table 4 and Table 5.

Particles volume fraction	S	$a/\mu\text{m}$	$b/\mu\text{m}$	E_c/GPa	Experimental result/GPa	relative error
3.0%	1	0.336	0.336	72.11	71.04	1.51%
	2	0.267	0.534	72.95		2.69%
	3	0.233	0.699	74.19		4.45%
5.6%	1	0.414	0.414	74.85	75.63	-1.03%
	2	0.329	0.658	77.53		2.52%
	3	0.287	0.861	83.19		10.00%
7.8%	1	0.463	0.463	77.49	77.77	-0.35%
	2	0.367	0.734	82.69		6.33%
	3	0.321	0.963	99.35		27.76%

Table 4: The predicted values of equivalent tensile modulus of nano-PRMMCs with different particles size and volume fraction

Particles volume fraction	S	$a/\mu\text{m}$	$b/\mu\text{m}$	E_c/GPa	Experimental result/GPa	relative error
3.0%	1	0.336	0.336	64.45	64.96	-0.78%
	2	0.267	0.534	65.23		0.42%
	3	0.233	0.699	66.40		2.22%
5.6%	1	0.414	0.414	65.15	65.59	-0.66%
	2	0.329	0.658	67.59		3.06%
	3	0.287	0.861	72.89		11.13%
7.8%	1	0.463	0.463	65.93	68.08	-3.15%
	2	0.367	0.734	70.57		3.66%
	3	0.321	0.963	86.30		26.77%

Table 5: The predicted values of equivalent compressive modulus of nano-PRMMCs with different particles size and volume fraction

Fig 9: The tensile modulus of PRMMCs predicted by Equation (1)

Fig 10: The compressive modulus of PRMMCs predicted by Equation (1)

The following conclusions can be deduced by analyzing Table 4 to 5 and Fig 9 to 10:

- a. Particles volume fraction is an important factor affecting the equivalent tensile and compressive modulus of in-situ $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al7050}$ composites. The equivalent tensile and compressive modulus increase with the increase of particles volume fraction respectively.

- b. The relative error between experimental results and values predicted by the Equation (1) increases with the increase of particles volume fraction. The relative error is less than 5% when particles volume fraction is less than 5.6%.
- c. Particles size also affects the accuracy of Equation (1) and the relative error is less than 3% when $S \leq 2$, but it's more than 10% when $S \geq 3$.
- d. The accuracy of the Equation (1) is improved 54.41% than that of the existing formulae^[9,10].

3.2 Numerical Simulation on Fracture Behaviors of Nano-PRMMCs

To Study the influence of particles on the fracture behavior of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites, the random distribution microstructure model of particles is built based on the SEM images of microstructure by combining image processing, CAD geometric modeling and finite element meshing techniques^[15,16]. The crack initiation, crack propagation and other fracture behavior of in-situ TiB₂/Al356 composites are simulated under the experimental loads by using FEM software ABAQUS based on the XFEM^[15] technique to get the path of crack propagation^[17]. Moreover the open-mode Stress Intensity Factors (SIF) K_I is simulated. The results of numerical simulations are shown in Fig 11 to 17.

Fig 11: The geometric model and the random distribution microstructure model of in-situ TiB₂/Al7050 composites, and the reviewed region.

The TiB₂ particles are replaced by circular particles and the reviewed region surrounded by the supposed homogeneous composites is shown in Fig 11 (c). The parameter r/W is defined to describe the effect of boundary condition, where r and W are the particles radius and the width of selected region respectively.

Fig 12: The road of crack propagation of geometry model-a, $r=1.5\mu\text{m}$.

Fig 13: The road of crack propagation of geometry model-b, $r=1.0\mu\text{m}$.

Fig 14: The road of crack propagation of geometry model-c, $r=0.8\mu\text{m}$.

Fig 15: The road of crack propagation of geometry model-d, $r=0.7\mu\text{m}$.

Fig 16: The road of crack propagation of geometry model-e, $r=0.4\mu\text{m}$.

Fig 17: The effect of particles radius on K_I of in-situ $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al7050}$ composites.

The following conclusions can be deduced by analyzing the Fig 11 to 17:

- In-situ $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al7050}$ composites with higher uniformity of particles distribution have higher ability to resist the initiation and propagation of cracks in the material.
- If the crack tip deviates from the center of particles, the crack will bypass the particles and continue to expand when particle radius is less than $0.5\mu\text{m}$; the particles will prevent crack propagation when particles radius ranges from $0.5\sim 1.0\mu\text{m}$; the particles will not only prevent crack propagation but also absorb stress and energy when particle radius is larger than $1.0\mu\text{m}$.
- The K_I will decrease with the increase of particles size and increase with more uniform particles distribution.

4 CONCLUSIONS

- The experimental results show that compressive modulus, tensile modulus and shear modulus of the in-situ $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al7050}$ composites with volume fraction 7.8% content of particles increase by 6.91%, 16.3% and 11.94% respectively compared with matrix Al7050. This improvement of the stiffness of in-situ $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al7050}$ composites is great, while the strength of in-situ $\text{TiB}_2/\text{Al7050}$ composites isn't improved greatly. Furthermore the elongation and Poisson's ratio are reduced slightly.
- A new model has been proposed based on the improvement of previous models and the accuracy of the Equation (1) is improved 54.41% than that of the existing formulae^[9,10]. The

relative error is less than 5% when particles volume fraction is less than 5.6%, moreover the smaller the particles aspect ratios S is, the smaller the relative error is.

- c. The numerical simulations results show that TiB_2 particles can prevent crack propagation effectively and even absorb the stress and energy when the crack tip meets particles. The K_I will decrease smoothly with the increase of particles size and volume fraction if the particles radius is smaller than $1.3\mu m$, but decrease rapidly when particles radius is larger than $1.3\mu m$. And the K_I increases with more uniform particles distribution.

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